
TECHNOLOGY OF DEVELOPMENT OF TECHNOETHICAL CULTURE AMONG STUDENTS OF HIGHER TECHNICAL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7871975>

Alimjonova Gulnozaxon Isroiljon qizi

g.alimjonova@ferpi.uz

ORCID(0000-0003-0280-6545)

**Independent Researcher, Fergana Polytechnic Institute UZBEKISTAN*

Annotatsiya.

Maqolada interfaol ta'lim usullaridan biri "fasilitatsiya" haqida so'z boradi. Usulning mohiyati tavsiflanadi, metodni qo'llash maqsadlari shakllantiriladi, o'quv jarayoniga moslashish imkoniyatlari, o'qituvchining "fasilitator" va "moderator" o'rtasidagi farqlar ko'rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlar.

interfaol ta'lim, interfaol ta'lim usuli, guruh ishini tashkil etish, fasilitator, fasilitatsiya

Annotatsion.

The article discusses one of the methods of interactive learning, which is called "facilitation". The essence of the method is described, the goals of applying the method are formulated, the possibility of adapting to the educational process, the differences between the teacher "facilitator" and "moderator" are considered, examples of adaptation of this technology to a particular discipline are given.

Ключевые слова.

интерактивное обучение метод интерактивного обучения, организация групповой работы, фасилитатор, фасилитация

Аннотация.

В статье рассматривается один из методов интерактивного обучения, который называется «фасилитация». Описывается сущность метода, формулируются цели применения метода, возможности адаптации к образовательному процессу, рассматриваются отличия педагога «фасилитатора» от «модератора», примеры адаптации данной технологии к конкретной дисциплине.

Key words.

interactive learning, interactive learning method, organization of group work, facilitator, facilitation.

In modern conditions, one of the necessary conditions for increasing the effectiveness of the development of technoethical culture among students of higher technical educational institutions is the organization of this process on a technological basis. Educational, pedagogic, educational, teaching technologies are distinguished in educational practice.

There are a number of reasons that increase the need for the development of technoethical culture in students. This is a complex and complex process that is directly related to the formation of a moral attitude of mankind towards technology, to stand in a position of high morality in the creation and use of technology. It is the technoethical culture that raises the student's responsible approach to the world of technology and knowledge to a new level. As a result, not only knowledge about technology, but also ideas about technical values begin to form in a unique way. As a result, the students of the technical direction develop the qualities of creativity and creativity, more precisely, the technoethical culture plays the role of an inspiring, inspiring, encouraging tool for the development of such qualities. Teaching the "Basics of Technoethical Culture" module and forming technoethical knowledge, worldview, qualifications and skills in this subject are of great importance in the development of technoethical culture of the student.

By teaching and analyzing the module "Basics of technoethical culture", the student's understanding of technology and technoethics will be enriched, his conclusions about the activity of technology and its possibilities will be expanded. The student will be able to make clear conclusions about the history of man-made civilization, his ideas about technology will be enriched. In this process, the educational importance of techno-ethical culture is particularly evident.

To form students of higher technical educational institutions as independent, responsible, socially mobilized individuals, in order to prepare them for successful socialization and finding a suitable place in the labor market, it is necessary to develop social skills in them, to define and develop their own activities. To implement such an approach, comprehensive support of students in the learning process is of great pedagogical importance.

In order to pedagogically support the process of development of technoethical culture among students of higher technical educational institutions, it is extremely

necessary to carefully study, correct, restore and develop their relationships. The main goal of supporting the requirements in the educational process is to ensure their intellectual, physical, spiritual, cultural and social development at the same time.

Along with the traditional types of work, it is also important to develop a facilitative educational technology for organizing independent learning activities in the pedagogical support of students of higher technical educational institutions.

Independent education plays an important role in the development of technoethical culture among students of higher technical educational institutions. The analysis shows that independent education is understood as such educational activity, in which, along with the acquisition of knowledge, the formation of skills is ensured.

Independent education is an active method of education that solves the task of the teacher and the educational task under his leadership. Independent education is the organization and implementation of specific activities of students in connection with the set goal. Independent works of students are activities based on their high level of activity, creativity, independent analysis, initiative.

Independent education is one of the forms of learning, in which students consciously set one or another tasks and goals, plan and implement activities, and self-evaluate.

Independent education has several specific features: the uniqueness of independent work as an active (active) method of education is based on actions that the student performs without the help of the teacher, he chooses the methods of performing these actions himself, improves many actions, in connection with the set goal controls them; of independent work

the second characteristic is reflected in self-control, which is considered a form of student activity management; the third characteristic is the evaluative activity, which is strongly related to self-control and plays an important role in self-control; independent work always ends with some result.

Changes in the socio-economic, political, and spiritual spheres taking place in our society in modern conditions accelerate the introduction of innovations into the education system. In particular, there is a need to change the forms and mechanisms of the conditions for organizing the educational process. This situation can be especially clearly observed in the field of higher technical education. From this point of view, the issue of facilitation approach is becoming more and more interesting in pedagogy and psychology.

The word "facilitation" is derived from the English language, "facilitate" means to help, ease, strengthen. Facilitation is a way of positively influencing the student, creating a positive atmosphere in the group, making learners believe in their own strength and supporting them in their independent activities.

Currently, social and pedagogical types of facilitation are shown separately. Social facilitation is a social psychological phenomenon. Social facilitation in Latin - "socialis facilitatar" - means social facilitation. Pedagogical facilitation serves to increase the effectiveness of education (teaching, education) based on supporting the activities of learners. In this case, qualitative development is achieved as a result of the use of a special communication method by the pedagogue in the pedagogical process.

It is known that the basis of pedagogical facilitation is the cooperative work of students in groups. In connection with the organization of independent work of students of higher technical education, a lot of attention is paid to the use of individual, group and collective forms of work. Special attention is paid to the formation of communicative competence in students through the formation of cooperation skills. Taking into account this aspect, within the framework of the research, the technology of organizing independent work was developed on the basis of pedagogical facilitation aimed at encouraging students' joint collaborative activities.

Table 1

Pedagogical facilitation is the technology of organizing students' independent work on the development of technoethical culture

Stages	Deegres			
	Dating	Understa nd	Analysis	Synthesi s
Kognitive				
About the activity				
Axiologic al				

The content of the technology reflects the cognitive - operational - axiological unit and the levels of independent work (acquaintance, understanding, analysis, and synthesis) that are manifested in each of these stages in a unique way.

The motivational stage of technology is manifested at the following levels: familiarization: through an independent work assignment, the student needs to remember and group what he has learned before; to be understood: the student is motivated to internally express the problem described in the independent work assignment; analytical: the student becomes interested in finding a solution to the problem reflected in the independent work assignment; about synthesis: the student has a desire to propose a solution to the problem reflected in the independent work assignment.

The cognitive-operational stage of technology is manifested as follows in connection with the four (acquaintance, understanding, analysis and synthesis) levels of organizing the independent work of students of higher technical education institutions: familiarization: the student determines the main concepts reflected in the independent work assignment; to be understood: the student interprets the situation described in the independent work assignment; analytical: the student completes an independent task and compares his thoughts with those of others; about synthesis: the student searches for an independent working solution.

The operational stage of technology has the following specific content: introductory: describes an independent work solution; to be understood: demonstrates in practice the solution of an independent work assignment; analytical: reveals the nature of the problem in the independent work assignment; synthesis: offers conclusions in connection with an independent work assignment.

Informational and didactic support of technology reflects the forms, methods and means of organizing students' independent work through pedagogical facilitation (**Table 2**).

Informational and didactic support of the technology of organizing independent work of the requirements of higher technical educational institutions by means of pedagogical facilitation

Technological stages	Forms	Facilitative learning strategies	Means
Kognitive	Individual, pair work, group, collective, training, lesson	Free Writing, Five Minute Essay, Based Essay, Ten Minute Essay	Textbook, mass media, learning module, slide presentation, handouts, information
About the		Two-Part Diary, Study Guide, Concept Analysis, Creative Quiz	

activity			Technology
Axiological		Problem situation, problem question, problem issue, case study, educational project	

1. The development of technoethical culture among students of higher technical educational institutions, in turn, requires an analytical and alternative approach to the analysis of man-made processes. It is appropriate to use the situational analysis (case-study) strategy in solving this task. The case study is a combination of the English words case - specific situation and study - education. This strategy, in contrast to the problem-based learning method, is based on making clear decisions based on the study of real situations.

2. The main category of the case study is "analysis". The category of analysis can be understood as the mental dissection or scientific investigation of an object. There are different classifications of analysis, and the classification of mass analysis can be defined as follows: systematic analysis, correlational analysis, factor analysis, statistical analysis, etc. All these types of analysis can be used within the framework of the case-study method, and this case further expands the possibilities of the method. A number of analytical activities that can be performed in the process of understanding and thinking about the situation can be involved in the case study. This, in turn, requires a high level of methodological culture from the pedagogue.

REFERENCES:

1. Alimjonova, G. (2021). Modern competencies in the techno-culture of future technical specialists. *CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGICS*, 2(06), 78-84.
2. Каримов, Ш. Т., & Хожиакбарова, Г. (2017). АНАЛОГ ЗАДАЧИ ГУРСА ДЛЯ ОДНОГО НЕКЛАССИЧЕСКОГО УРАВНЕНИЯ ТРЕТЬЕГО ПОРЯДКА С СИНГУЛЯРНЫМ КОЭФФИЦИЕНТОМ. *TURIN POLYTECHNIC UNIVERSITY IN TASHKENT*, 121.
3. Alimjonova, G. (2021). The need for integration of social and technical knowledge in the development of technological culture of students of higher technical educational institutions. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(3), 502-510.

4. Алимжоновна, Г. И. Қ., & Назарова, Г. А. (2022). ТЕХНОЭТИК МАДАНИЯТ ТУШУНЧАСИНИНГ МАЗМУН-МОҲИЯТИ, УНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШНИНГ ПЕДАГОГИК ЗАРУРИЯТИ. *Scientific progress*, 3(4), 181-186.
5. Алимжоновна, Г. И. Қ., & Назарова, Г. А. (2022). АНАЛИТИК ТАФАККУРНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШНИНГ ПЕДАГОГИК ЗАРУРАТИ. *Scientific progress*, 3(4), 187-196.
6. Қизи, Г. А. И. (2022). ТЕХНОЭТИК МАДАНИЯТ ТУШУНЧАСИНИНГ МАЗМУН-МОҲИЯТИ, УНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШНИНГ ПЕДАГОГИК ЗАРУРАТИ. *INTEGRATION OF SCIENCE, EDUCATION AND PRACTICE. SCIENTIFIC-METHODICAL JOURNAL*, 3(3), 329-333.
7. Abdurahmonovna, N. G. (2022). Will Be on the Basis of Modern Economic Education Principles of Pedagogical Development of Analytical Thinking in Economists. *European Multidisciplinary Journal of Modern Science*, 6, 627-632.
8. Abdurahmonovna, N. G. (2022). Factors for the Development of Creativity and Critical Thinking in Future Economists Based on Analytical Thinking. *Journal of Ethics and Diversity in International Communication*, 2(5), 70-74.
9. Nazarova, G. A. (2022). Will be on the basis of modern economic education Principles of pedagogical development of analytical thinking in economists. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 9579-9585